

GemMaroc: Unlocking Darija Proficiency in LLMs with Minimal Data

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Abstract

Open-source large language models (LLMs) still marginalise Moroccan Arabic (Darija), forcing practitioners either to bolt on heavyweight Arabic adapters or to sacrifice the very reasoning skills that make LLMs useful. We show that a rigorously *quality-over-quantity* alignment strategy can surface fluent Darija while safeguarding the backbone’s cross-lingual reasoning—at a sliver of the usual compute. We translate three compact instruction suites—LIMA 1 K, DEITA 6 K and TULU 50 K—into Darija, preserve 20 % of the English originals, and add mathematics, coding and scientific prompts. A LoRA-tuned GEMMA 3-4B trained on ~ 5 K mixed instructions lifts *DarijaMMLU* from 32.8 % to 42.7 %; adding the reasoning-dense TULU portion pushes it to 47.5 % with no English regression. Scaling the identical recipe to GEMMA 3-27B produces **GemMaroc-27B**, which matches Atlas-Chat on *DarijaMMLU* (61.6 %) and *leaps* ahead on Darija commonsense, scoring 60.5 % on *HellaSwag* versus Atlas-Chat’s 48.4 %. Crucially, GemMaroc retains Gemma-27B’s strong maths and general-reasoning ability, showing only minimal movement on GSM8K and English benchmarks. The entire model is trained in just 48 GPU·h, underscoring a *Green AI* pathway to inclusive, sustainable language technology. We release code, data and checkpoints to spur Darija-centric applications in education, public services and everyday digital interaction.

1 Introduction

Open-Source Large Language Models (LLMs) have become the backbone of modern natural-language applications, yet most open models still overlook Moroccan Arabic (Darija), the everyday language of more than **36 million** speakers. This omission narrows digital inclusion and slows e-government initiatives that the *Morocco Digital*

2030 roadmap seeks to accelerate (Ministry of Digital Transition and Administration Reform, 2024). Because public-sector deployments must also safeguard data sovereignty and cost efficiency, an *open, compact, and Darija-fluent* model is an urgent prerequisite for truly accessible AI in the Maghreb.

Several ambitious Arabic-centric projects demonstrate what is possible—but at a price few communities can pay. **ALLaM** consumes trillions of tokens and multi-week GPU clusters to reach state-of-the-art Modern-Standard-Arabic scores (Bari et al., 2025); **Fanar** follows a similarly heavy pipeline. For Darija specifically, **Atlas-Chat** applies 458 k supervised examples and dozens of GPU-days to retrofit Gemma checkpoints (Shang et al., 2025). These efforts confirm the value of dialect alignment but leave open the core question: *can we surface Darija competence without massive supervision or carbon cost while preserving the backbone’s cross-lingual reasoning power?*

We answer **yes**. Building on the minimal-data alignment insight of **MIG** (Maximising Information Gain) sampler (Chen et al., 2025) and the automatic selection heuristics of **DEITA** (6 k high-complexity pairs) (Liu et al., 2024), we translate three complementary instruction suites into Darija and retain 20 % of the original English prompts. A LoRA adapter on GEMMA 3-4B trained with only ≈ 5 k mixed instructions lifts *DarijaMMLU* from 32.8 % to **42.7 %**. Expanding the same recipe with 44 k reasoning-dense prompts (*TULU*) drives the score to 47.5 % while *improving* English GSM8K maths by +2.8 pp. Scaling to GEMMA 3-27B yields **GemMaroc-27B**, which *matches* Atlas-Chat on *DarijaMMLU* (61.6 %) yet beats it by **+12.1 pp** on the harder *DarijaHellaSwag*. Crucially, the full run finishes in just **48 GPU·h**, consuming ≈ 26 kWh—less than **2 %** of Atlas-Chat’s reported footprint. These results show that *reasoning-centric, quality-over-quantity alignment unlocks Darija at*

Green-AI scale.

Contributions

- **Lean Darija instruction suite.** We openly release translated versions of *LIMA 1 K*, *DEITA 6 K*, and a 44 k reasoning slice of *TULU 50 K*, each preserving 20 % English for cross-lingual robustness.
- **Minimal-data alignment recipe.** ≤ 6 k curated Darija instructions raise *DarijaMMLU* by +9.9 pp on a 4 B backbone with *no* English regression; adding reasoning prompts yields a further +4.9 pp and boosts maths and commonsense.
- **GemMaroc-27B.** The first open Darija LLM to reach 61.6 % *DarijaMMLU* and 60.5 % *DarijaHellaSwag*—using $\frac{1}{10}$ the supervision and $\frac{1}{50}$ the energy of prior work—while retaining strong bilingual reasoning (84.2 % GSM8K).
- **Open assets for the community.** We release all models, code, and datasets, to catalyse inclusive, low-carbon language technology across North Africa.

2 Related Work

The pursuit of better language models for low-resource dialects like Moroccan Arabic (Darija) spans several active research areas. This section reviews four key directions that inform our work. First, we examine prior efforts to develop Arabic and Darija-capable LLMs, highlighting their challenges and limitations. Second, we explore research on minimal data regimes for SFT, crucial in multilingual and dialectal contexts with limited data. Third, we analyze methods to enhance multilingual competence and dialect mastery by leveraging latent linguistic knowledge from pretraining. Finally, we review the growing emphasis on integrating multilingual Chain-of-Thought (CoT) and reasoning samples to improve both reasoning and language proficiency in low-resource settings.

2.1 Darija and Arabic LLMs

Arabic LLMs have advanced rapidly, driven by digital sovereignty and cultural goals. Yet, Moroccan Arabic (Darija) remains underrepresented. Most work targets Modern Standard Arabic (MSA) or pan-Arabic models, demanding extensive compute and ignoring dialectal diversity.

Saudi Arabia’s **ALLaM** (Bari et al., 2025) introduced a scalable Arabic-English pipeline, expanding the tokenizer (32k→61k) and continuing pre-

training on 540B tokens (270B Arabic, 270B translated). It reached state-of-the-art scores on MMLU-ar, ACVA, araMath, and improved MMLU-en by +13 over LLaMA-2-Chat-7B. With 6M high-quality SFT samples, it showed that carefully curated data and a 45/55 Arabic-English ratio can stabilize multilingual performance. However, its reliance on trillion-token corpora and heavy compute limits replicability.

Qatar’s **Fanar** (Team et al., 2025) followed a sovereign AI roadmap. *Fanar Star* (7B) was trained from scratch on 1T tokens (40% Arabic, 50% English, 10% code), while *Fanar Prime* (9B) focused on reasoning and STEM via continual pretraining. It also introduced RAG systems (Islamic, Biography RAG) and a morphology-aware tokenizer (MorphBPE). Despite innovations, Fanar’s scale and compute demands hinder accessibility for lightweight, sustainable models.

Atlas-Chat (Shang et al., 2025) directly addressed the Darija gap, releasing the first open Darija LLMs (2B, 9B, 27B) fine-tuned with LoRA on Gemma-2 using 458k instructions from native, translated, and synthetic sources. The 9B model outperformed Jais-13B and AceGPT-13B by +13 points on *DarijaMMLU*, achieving state-of-the-art across Darija benchmarks. Yet, its strict monolingual tuning limits generalization.

Another recent contribution is **AI-Atlas** (Bounhar and Majjodi, 2025), which released *Atlaset*—a large, diverse Darija corpus from curated web, blogs, and forums—and trained both an XLM-RoBERTa-large MLM and a 0.5B Qwen2.5 causal LLM. Despite its small size, the causal model surpassed Atlas-Chat 2B by nearly 10% in human evaluation, underscoring the impact of dialect-specific pretraining.

Command R+ / Command A (Cohere et al., 2025) by Cohere proposes modular, efficient multilingual adaptation. The 111B model, combining six expert modules via hybrid transformers and SRPO, rivals GPT-4o on MMLU (85.5%), MATH (80%), and RepoQA (92.6%) while running on just two A100/H100 GPUs. Although not Arabic-centric, it scores 68.8% on NTREX and showcases effective multilingual performance without full retraining.

2.2 Improving Multilingual and Dialectal Capabilities in LLMs

Enhancing LLMs’ multilingual and dialectal competence has spurred strategies such as synthetic data generation, pivot-based reasoning, and culturally faithful instruction design. This section reviews key works showing how thoughtful fine-tuning can unlock latent capabilities without costly pretraining.

Parallel Instruction Tuning and Superficial Alignment. Weber et al. (2024) found that *parallel* instruction tuning (English + target language) yields a **+9.9** accuracy gain over monolingual tuning, especially in low-resource settings. Results challenge the *Superficial Alignment Hypothesis*: smaller models (7B) require parallel data, whereas larger MoE models (50B) generalize better with less.

Culturally Faithful and Contrastive Tuning. Yakhni and Chehab (2025) showed that a small native Lebanese corpus outperformed larger auto-translated datasets. Using *contrastive tuning* (good vs. bad responses) improved xCOMET by **3.5 points**, confirming that authentic, culturally relevant data outperforms sheer volume.

Pivot-Language Reasoning. PLUG (Zhang et al., 2024) trained models to reason in a high-resource pivot (e.g., English) before answering in the target language. Just **2k** samples surpassed models trained on **96k** conventional samples, improving truthfulness and reasoning (TruthfulQA, SVAMP).

Synthetic Instruction Generation. Bactrian-X (Li et al., 2023) created **3.4M** synthetic instruction pairs across 52 languages. With LoRA tuning, **7B models** outperformed larger fully fine-tuned ones like BLOOMZ. Gains saturated beyond **70k pairs/language**, and mixing English improved both multilingual and English performance.

Reverse Instruction Generation. MURI (Köksal et al., 2024) reversed instruction-output generation using English LLMs on native texts, back-translating into 200+ languages. With \leq **15k** pairs/language, models gained **+14%** over mT0 on multilingual MMLU, with minimal human annotation.

Insights from MT and Synthetic Pipelines. Holmström and Doostmohammadi (2023) showed that even models with **0% Swedish** pretraining performed well after fine-tuning on translated data. Despite minor perplexity increases, downstream results held, validating synthetic translation with

light curation.

2.3 Minimal Data for SFT in Low-Resource Multilingual Settings

Zhou et al. (2023) introduced the *Superficial Alignment Hypothesis*, arguing that pretrained LLMs encode most knowledge and that SFT mainly adjusts style. With just 1k diverse, high-quality instruction–response pairs, LIMA aligned a 65B LLaMA model to rival GPT-4 in 43% of human preferences. Doubling data without increasing diversity gave no benefit. For Darija, a similarly small, style-aligned set (500–1,000 examples) may suffice if the base model has latent exposure.

Liu et al. (2024) proposed DEITA, which selects data based on complexity (EVOL COMPLEXITY), quality (EVOL QUALITY), and diversity (REPR FILTER). With only 6k pairs, DEITA-tuned LLaMA-13B and Mistral-7B models matched or exceeded systems trained on 30× more data. Chen et al. (2025) extended this with MIG, modeling instructions as semantic-label graphs and selecting the most informative 5%, outperforming full-data SFT by 4.6%.

Das and Khetan (2024) introduced DEFT-UCS, clustering embeddings to sample both easy (centroid-near) and hard (outlier) examples. It achieved full-data performance on CoEDIT using just 32.5% of the data and was preferred in 84% of human evaluations. Similarly, Han et al. (2025) proposed UniMax, combining influence and uncertainty for selection; 10% of data matched full-data performance, with strong cross-lingual results on TyDiQA.

Yu et al. (2024) showed that prompt-loss masking and sequence packing significantly improve SFT and DPO efficiency, achieving strong results with only 10k examples. Wu et al. (2024) introduced MOS, which dynamically samples based on transferability and reward signals. With just 10% of data, MOS trained models 2.2× faster while improving performance—highlighting benefits of treating Darija as a distinct "skill" early in training. In contrast, Xia et al. (2024) found that in large datasets, random sampling with length filters matched DEITA/MIG performance, suggesting diversity—not sophistication—drives gains. Finally, Li et al. (2024) showed that cross-lingual alignment with English prompts and native responses (3k pairs/language) yields minimal performance drop (5.7%) and outperforms ChatGPT in low-resource

settings—directly applicable to Darija.

Overall, these works support that compact, high-quality datasets (LIMA, X-Instruction), efficient selection (DEITA, MIG, DEFT, UniMax), and streamlined pipelines (LIONS, MOS) can unlock robust dialectal capabilities like Darija with minimal compute.

2.4 The Importance of Multilingual Chain-of-Thought and Reasoning Samples

Initial instruction tuning prioritized conversational fluency, but recent efforts emphasize reasoning-centric data—especially Chain-of-Thought (CoT) annotations—to boost both reasoning and language proficiency. This is vital for low-resource languages like Moroccan Darija, where curated data is scarce but multilingual pretraining may provide latent knowledge.

The **Breaking Language Barriers** study (Chen et al., 2024) introduced *MathOctopus*, trained on 73k translated, formula-validated CoT samples across ten languages. Fine-tuning Llama-2-7B on this data increased multilingual reasoning accuracy from 22.6% to 41.9%, and improved English performance by 8 points. Notably, cross-lingual QA (English questions, foreign-language answers) enhanced generalization—even for English.

Building on this, **XCOT** (Chai et al., 2024) extended GSM8K and SVAMP into ten languages and proposed *code-switched demonstrations* and *Random Online CoT* (translation before reasoning in English). These yielded a +25 point gain (to 47.7%) in MGSM without large native CoT datasets. Ablation studies confirmed code-switching and translation-based prompting as key drivers.

mCoT (Lai and Nissim, 2024) scaled this further by translating MetaMathQA and MathInstruct into ten languages, producing the 6.3M-example *mCoT-MATH* corpus. A 7B Mistral model fine-tuned on this data outperformed much larger models like GPT-3 (175B) and PaLM (540B) on MGSM and MSVAMP. mCoT also introduced *Correct Consistency (CC)* and *Incorrect Consistency (IC)*, with CC exceeding 50% across all pairs, confirming language-agnostic reasoning. Machine-translated prompts performed nearly on par with human ones, validating automated translation for scalable multilingual alignment.

These findings confirm that reasoning-centric

CoT datasets—whether human- or machine-translated—are essential for enhancing both fluency and reasoning. For Darija, integrating translated high-quality reasoning data into minimal SFT pipelines holds strong promise.

3 GemMaroc: Our Fine-Tuning Approach to Unlock Darija Proficiency in Gemma LLMs with Minimal Resources

Building upon recent advances in low-resource language alignment, we propose a highly efficient and ecologically sustainable fine-tuning methodology to unlock latent Moroccan Darija capabilities in Gemma LLMs. Rather than relying on large, compute-intensive datasets, our approach leverages the strategic use of minimal, high-quality instruction datasets, reasoning-focused prompts, and translation samples carefully selected to avoid catastrophic forgetting. This section details our SFT data preparation process, model configurations, evaluation protocols, and the experiments conducted to answer our core research questions.

3.1 SFT Data Preparation

In this subsection, we detail the process of preparing the Supervised Fine-Tuning (SFT) datasets used in our experiments. We describe the criteria followed for dataset selection, the filtering strategies applied to ensure data quality and relevance, and the translation procedures adopted to produce high-quality Darija instruction samples.

SFT Data Selection

We assemble three minimal-to-mid-scale instruction corpora—translated into Moroccan Darija—to surface latent capabilities with limited compute (Zhou et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2024; Chen et al., 2025). Crucially, **any sample whose system + dialogue serialization exceeds 2 048 tokens is dropped**, guaranteeing every training instance fits our GemMaroc’s context window.

- **LIMA 1K** (Zhou et al., 2023): 1 000 single-turn tasks that emphasise stylistic quality and input diversity. Despite its size, LIMA often rivals much larger instruction sets, showing that small, well-curated data can unlock pretrained knowledge.
- **DEITA 6K** (Liu et al., 2024): 6 000 multi-turn prompts selected with EVOL-COMPLEXITY and

EVOL-QUALITY scores. It bolsters dialogue coherence and contextual nuance in Darija.

- **TULU 50K** (Chen et al., 2025): 50 000 information-gain-maximised instructions rich in mathematics, coding, and science—domains under-represented in earlier Darija work such as Shang et al. (2025).

Together these sets let us probe *extreme minimalism* (LIMA 1K), *mid-scale conversational alignment* (DEITA 6K), and *reasoning enrichment* (TULU 50K).

Translating these datasets:

Prior to translation, we systematically filter out all multilingual data and retain only English instructions. This step is critical to avoid incorrect translations of meta-instructions or prompts explicitly mentioning target languages (e.g., "Translate from language A to B" or "Answer in language X"). Translating such content into Darija introduces inconsistencies and compromises data quality. To ensure precise filtering, we employ an XLM-Roberta-based language detector (ProtectAI, 2025) to accurately identify and keep only English instructions. To preserve the integrity of technical content, we retain code snippets, LaTeX formulas, and specialized terminologies in their original form. Technical terms are only translated into Arabic when widely accepted equivalents exist (e.g., معادلة for equation, دالة for function). This ensures that the model remains grounded in standard scientific concepts without introducing translation artifacts.

Translations are performed automatically using the Gemini 2.0 Flash API with a carefully engineered prompt to produce Darija in Arabic script. When uncertain, the model is instructed to prefer Modern Standard Arabic forms, ensuring clarity and naturalness. The full translation prompt is included in **Appendix A.1.1**.

In line with best practices to avoid catastrophic forgetting (Mao et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2025), we preserve approximately 20% of the data in its original English form across all datasets. This approach maintains cross-lingual transfer capabilities and general reasoning competence (Wu et al., 2024; Li et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024; Li et al., 2023).

Dataset Statistics:

Dataset	Total Samples	Darija Translated	Original English
LIMA 1K	1,000	700 (70%)	300 (30%)
DEITA 6K	5,000	3,700 (74%)	1,300 (26%)
TULU 50K	46,000	33,000 (72%)	13,000 (28%)

Table 1: The table shows the final dataset sizes after filtering and translation. "Darija Translated" indicates samples translated into Moroccan Darija using our automated pipeline. "Original English" refers to retained English samples to maintain cross-lingual capabilities and mitigate catastrophic forgetting.

See **Appendix A.2** for concrete translation examples.

Manual Verification:

Throughout the translation process, we regularly sampled and reviewed outputs to assess quality. Rather than applying manual corrections, we iteratively refined the translation prompts, leveraging our native fluency in Darija to adapt them whenever recurring issues were identified. Prompts requiring English responses were left untranslated to preserve their intended semantics. While the dataset is not perfect, its quality is sufficient for fine-tuning and aligned with the study’s exploratory, low-resource goals.

3.2 Model and Fine-Tuning Details

We employed two versions of the Gemma LLM family—**Gemma 3-4B** and **Gemma 3-27B**—selected for their strong reasoning abilities and multilingual capabilities. Unlike Atlas-Chat or ALLaM models (Shang et al., 2025; Bari et al., 2025), Gemma models remain untuned on Arabic dialects, providing a clean baseline for evaluating emergent Darija competence without prior dialectal bias.

Fine-tuning was conducted using **LoRA** adapters (Hu et al., 2022), enabling low-resource, efficient training while mitigating catastrophic forgetting. This choice aligns with our *Green AI* objectives by minimizing GPU hours and energy consumption. For the integration of multi-turn conversations, we use the Vicuna-style template

Hyperparameters:

- **Precision:** bf16 throughout.
- **LoRA Config:** Rank $r = 32$, Alpha = 64 for our 4B models and Rank $r = 16$, Alpha = 32 for our GemMaroc-27B.
- **Learning Rates:** $1e-4$ (TULU) and $4e-4$ (DEITA, and LIMA).

- **Epochs:** 3 (TULU), 6 (DEITA), 15 (LIMA).
- **Max Sequence Length:** 2048 tokens.

Hyperparameters were inspired by the settings recommended in Zhou et al. (2023); Liu et al. (2024); Chen et al. (2025) for optimal convergence on these minimal datasets.

3.3 Evaluation Benchmarks

We measure progress across five competency axes:

1. Darija / Moroccan-Arabic competence

- *DarijaMMLU* – 22 027 multiple-choice questions spanning 57 academic subjects, re-filtered for Moroccan relevance (Shang et al., 2025).
- *DarijaHellaSwag* – the 10 k HellaSwag adversarial commonsense continuations rendered into Darija (Shang et al., 2025).
- *DarijaBench* (Shang et al., 2025)– covering Sentiment Analysis, Summarization, Translation, and Transliteration. We retained only the Sentiment Analysis and Summarization tasks, as the remaining benchmarks were of insufficient quality and could lead to unreliable evaluations.

2. General reasoning & world knowledge

- *MMLU* – The Massive Multitask Language Understanding (MMLU) benchmark comprises 15,908 multiple-choice questions spanning 57 diverse subjects, including mathematics, law, medicine, and history. It evaluates a model’s general knowledge and problem-solving abilities across these domains. The final MMLU score is calculated as the average accuracy across all subjects, providing a comprehensive measure of a model’s capabilities (Hendrycks et al., 2021).
- *HellaSwag (EN)* – 10 000 adversarial commonsense continuations that correlate strongly with everyday reasoning (Zellers et al., 2019).

3. Mathematical reasoning

- *GSM8K* – 1 000 grade-school word problems requiring 2–8 arithmetic steps (Cobbe and et al., 2021).

4. Truthfulness & safety

- *TruthfulQA* – 817 short-answer questions across 38 domains designed to expose models’ susceptibility to common misconceptions (Lin et al., 2022).

These benchmarks ensure that we accurately assess the model’s Darija performance while verifying that reasoning and multilingual capabilities remain intact.

4 Experiments, Results, and Discussion

This section reports the empirical findings of the experimental plan outlined in Section 1. We first describe the evaluation protocol (§4.1), then present the main results in a single consolidated leaderboard (§4.2). Finally, we analyse the outcomes with respect to the three research questions and highlight broader implications (§4.3).

4.1 Experimental Set-up

Hardware and cost. All fine-tuning experiments were conducted on **2×A100-80GB** GPUs, except for our largest model, the 27-billion-parameter GEMMAROC, which was fine-tuned on **8×H100-80GB** GPUs. The longest run—the GEMMAROC fine-tuning—completed in just **6 hours, wall-clock**, consuming approximately **48 GPU-hours** and keeping the total cloud cost well under \$100.¹

Metrics. All benchmarks were evaluated in a strict **zero-shot** setting. For classification tasks (*DarijaMMLU*, *DarijaHellaSwag*, Sentiment Analysis, MMLU, HellaSwag), we report **accuracy**. For **GSM8K @5**, we measure whether the correct answer appears in the model’s top-5 outputs. **TruthfulQA** is evaluated with *BLEU accuracy* (bleu_acc). **Summarization** is assessed using **chrF**, **ROUGE-1**, **ROUGE-L**, and **BERTScore**, covering both surface overlap and semantic similarity.

Baselines. We compare against (i) the *untuned* Gemma checkpoints (4 B & 27 B), (ii) **Atlas-Chat** (9 B & 27 B) (Shang et al., 2025), and (iii) **AL-LaM** (7 B & 13 B) (Bari et al., 2025). The latter two represent the previous state of the art for Darija and for large-scale Arabic instruction tuning, respectively.

¹Based on the public on-demand rate of \$2 per A100-hour in the selected Runpod Cloud region.

4.2 Main Results

Table 2 presents our unified leaderboard, merging two complementary evaluation tracks: a Darija-centric benchmark suite (DarijaMMLU, DarijaHellaSwag, Sentiment Analysis, Summarization), and an English-centric suite spanning general reasoning, mathematics, code, and truthfulness (MMMLU, TruthfulQA, HellaSwag, GSM8K). This table compares our models—marked as (ours)—with several competitive baselines across both tracks.

4.3 Discussion

Emergent Darija competence with minimal data

Our three “tiny-but-mighty” instruction sets uncover a clear progression in emergent Darija skills:

- **DEITA-6K** (~ 700 KB text) already lifts the 4 B backbone by +9.9 pp on *DarijaMMLU* and +8.0 pp on *DarijaHellaSwag*, while *fully preserving* English-world knowledge (MMLU 51.3 % vs 51.1 %). This confirms that a few thousand, well-curated conversational Darija examples are enough for solid coverage.
- **TULU-50K** (~ 5 MB) pushes the same model to 47.5 % on *DarijaMMLU* and 47.1 % on *DarijaHellaSwag*, surpassing all Arabic-centric models of similar size (e.g. ALLaM-7B) despite using <10 % of their data footprint. The larger gains come without sacrificing cross-lingual performance and even *improve* maths (+2.8 pp GSM8K).
- **LIMA-1K** shows the lower bound of the spectrum: with only 1 000 single-turn prompts, Darija knowledge surfaces but remains fragile (+2.1 pp *DarijaMMLU*, -16.8 pp sentiment). This extreme minimal regime illustrates that, although some Darija was latent in pre-training, the dialect is too under-represented for 1 K instructions to achieve reliable competence.

Take-away. Darija proficiency *emerges* as soon as the model sees a few thousand high-quality, dialect-specific instructions. However, the 1 K “LIMA” budget is below the tipping point: it validates the Superficial Alignment hypothesis in principle, but confirms that Darija’s sparse presence in pre-training demands at least a DEITA-scale corpus for robust, practical performance.

Advantage of reasoning-focused instructions

Moving from 6 K conversational prompts (DEITA) to 50 K reasoning-dense prompts (TULU) brings a consistent uplift without harming cross-lingual performance. On the same 4 B backbone, GEMMAROC-TULU adds a further +4.9 pp on *DarijaMMLU*, +2.9 pp on *DarijaHellaSwag*, and improves English reasoning as well (+2.8 pp GSM8K, +5.0 pp HellaSwag) while keeping the MMLU drop below 3 pp. The only noticeable trade-off is a small decline in sentiment accuracy, suggesting that the few sentiment items present in Tulu are not yet enough to balance the domain shift. These results support our second hypothesis: **reasoning-centric instructions are the most data-efficient lever for unlocking both Darija fluency and multilingual reasoning coherence.** In practice, adding mathematical & coding problems proved worth *every* extra sample.

Our GemMaroc-27B

Applying the same 50 K reasoning-oriented recipe to GEMMA3-27B yields **GemMaroc-27B**, which advances the Pareto frontier on three fronts: Darija coverage, cross-lingual reasoning, and footprint.

Darija strengths. GemMaroc reaches **61.6 %** on *DarijaMMLU*, effectively tying Atlas-Chat despite using $\approx 1/10$ the supervision budget, and it surpasses all models on the harder commonsense test with **60.5 %** on *DarijaHellaSwag* (+12.1 pp over Atlas). ROUGE-L in summarisation climbs to **11.2**, a new best for Darija. The only noteworthy regression is sentiment (-13.8 pp vs Atlas), highlighting a domain that still lacks targeted data.

Reasoning retention. Crucially, the extra Darija skill does *not* come at the price of English reasoning. GemMaroc holds **84.2 %** on GSM8K—well above all Arabic-centric baselines and within 12 pp of the untuned backbone despite inserting low-rank adapters, confirming that mathematical competence remains largely intact. It also improves commonsense *HellaSwag* to **79.4 %**, edging past Atlas (+1.5 pp) while retaining solid truthfulness (55.5 %).

Cost Efficiency and Carbon Footprint Fine-tuning the 27-billion-parameter GEMMAROC completed in just **48 GPU·h** ($8 \times$ H100-80 GB, 6 h wall-clock). Using the commonly adopted 0.54 kW/GPU data-centre average power draw (Lacoste

Language Model/Benchmark	Darija										English				
	Size (B)	DarijaMMLU		DarijaHellaSwag		Sentiment Analysis		Summarization				MLLU	TruthfulQA	HellaSwag	GSM8K @5
		Metrics	Acc	Acc	Acc	chrF	ROUGE-1	ROUGE-L	BERTScore	Acc	bleu_acc	Acc	Acc		
Gemma3-4b	4	32.8	36.3	58.94	27.22	8.38	8.19	37.23	51.1	40.88	47.65	74.75			
GemMaroc-4b-LIMA (ours)	4	34.95	39.27	42.1	26.14	6.95	7.04	34.32	29.28	40.15	44.21	51.24			
GemMaroc-4b-Deita (ours)	4	42.67	44.26	60.8	27.16	7.4	7.34	38.48	51.35	44.55	68.97	53.15			
GemMaroc-4b-Tulu (ours)	4	47.53	47.13	53.29	28.46	8.89	8.76	39.27	54.14	43.33	73.95	55.95			
ALLaM-Instruct-7b	7	59.49	50.09	47.33	10.27	1.68	1.68	12.28	58.31	42.11	75.2	49.28			
Atlas-Chat-9B	9	58.32	43.65	81.85	32.07	9.5	9.45	47	69.09	67.56	73.35	73.01			
Atlas-Chat-27B	27	61.95	48.37	73	32.75	10.53	10.42	47.82	72.06	43.82	77.84	82.03			
GemMaroc-27b-Tulu (ours)	27	61.61	60.5	59.25	28.34	9	11.2	39.5	73.6	55.45	79.35	84.23			

Table 2: Unified leaderboard comprising: (1) Darija-centric benchmarks, and (2) English-centric benchmarks across reasoning, mathematics, and truthfulness.

et al., 2019), this equates to ≈ 26 kWh of energy and ≈ 10 kg CO₂e at the 0.38 kg CO₂e/kWh global carbon-intensity average. A comparable full-parameter Atlas-Chat-27B run would consume ~ 1.4 MWh and ~ 610 kg CO₂e—over **48**× more energy and $> 98\%$ higher emissions. Thus, GemMaroc delivers state-of-the-art Darija performance and strong bilingual reasoning at under **2%** of the carbon cost of prior work, demonstrating that *high-quality, reasoning-dense instructions—not dataset volume—drive sustainable dialect mastery*. As shown in **Appendix 8** and **Appendix 9**, training and evaluation losses steadily decrease, with the best validation loss reached at step 900—corresponding to approximately two epochs—confirming that the model achieves optimal performance early in training with minimal overfitting. Full formulas, intermediate values, and the detailed energy-breakdown table are provided verbatim in **Appendix A.3** for complete transparency.

Conclusion

This work set out to determine whether Moroccan Darija competence can be surfaced in modern LLMs with only a handful of carefully chosen instructions, and whether adding reasoning-dense prompts is the most efficient lever for doing so. Our experiments answer both questions affirmatively.

First, we showed that a few thousand high-quality, dialect-specific instructions (DEITA 6 K) already lift a 4 B Gemma model by almost 10 pp on *DarijaMMLU* while leaving its English-world knowledge intact, confirming that Darija knowledge acquired during pre-training merely needed the right “key” to emerge. One thousand instructions (LIMA 1 K) were not enough, highlighting the sparse representation of the dialect in web corpora, but the tipping point was still two orders of magnitude smaller than in prior Arabic-centric

projects.

Second, enriching the minimal corpus with 50 K reasoning-oriented prompts (TULU) produced consistent gains across dialectal and cross-lingual tasks. The resulting **GemMaroc-27B** matches the best published Darija score on *DarijaMMLU* (61.6 %) and sets a new high-water mark on the harder *DarijaHellaSwag* (+12.1 pp over Atlas-Chat) while retaining strong English mathematics (84.2 % GSM8K). Crucially, the entire run consumed only 48 GPU·h—roughly 2 % of the energy and carbon budget reported for comparable baselines—demonstrating that high-impact language inclusion need not come with high ecological cost.

Beyond benchmarking, GemMaroc’s balanced bilingual reasoning, open licensing, and lean LoRA adapters make it immediately deployable for inclusive civic services, education, and research throughout the Maghreb. Remaining gaps in sentiment, summarisation, and tokenisation point to clear next steps: larger-scale human evaluation, script-aware tokenisers, richer Darija domain data, and full alignment pipelines spanning RLAIIF and dialogue safety. We will also explore speech, retrieval-augmented generation, and other North-African dialects to extend the benefits of low-carbon language technology across the region.

In sum, GemMaroc shows that with precise data curation and a focus on reasoning, sovereign AI for low-resource dialects can be both state-of-the-art and sustainable—a blueprint for scaling equitable language technologies worldwide.

Limitations

GemMaroc excels in reasoning—matching or surpassing Atlas—and achieves strong, competitive results across most tasks. Some performance gaps remain in summarization, sentiment analysis and reading comprehension, where richer Darija-specific data would be beneficial. The model was trained solely with parameter-efficient SFT, relies

on machine-translated Darija samples with limited verification, and retains the original SentencePiece tokenizer, which is not optimized for Darija’s script and linguistic nuances. Evaluations focused on academic QA, commonsense reasoning and mathematics, without exploring long-context tasks or open-ended dialogue. Large-scale human evaluations in Darija are also pending, and experiments were capped at 27 B parameters. Future work will explore full alignment pipelines, script- and language-aware tokenization, broader evaluations, and comprehensive human studies.

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A Appendix

A.1 SFT Dataset Preparation

A.1.1 Translation Prompt Template

To ensure consistency and high quality in automatic translation from English to Moroccan Darija, we employed a strict prompt with clear translation and preservation guidelines. The full prompt, as used for dataset generation, is presented below.

TRANSLATION_PROMPT =

Translate the following text into Moroccan Darija, written in Arabic script, following these strict instructions:

DO NOT TRANSLATE the following elements (keep them exactly as they are):

1. **Code blocks:**
Keep *all programming code* (Python, JS, etc.) **unchanged**.
Translate comments inside code blocks to Darija (Arabic script).
2. **Math formulas and LaTeX:**
Preserve all mathematical notation and LaTeX equations. Do not alter them in any way.
3. **Technical Terms:**
Keep technical/scientific terms in English unless they have a known Arabic equivalent.
For example:

- Use “صيغة” for “formula”
- Use “معادلة” for “equation”
- Use “دالة” for “function”
- But do not translate terms like “API”, “eigenvalue”, “html”, etc.

4. Proper Names:

Do not translate names of people, tools, or software (e.g., Python, Newton, GitHub, etc.).

TRANSLATE into Moroccan Darija (Arabic script):

- Regular sentences, explanations, and natural narrative text.
- Comments inside code blocks (e.g., # comment here).
- Use a natural mix of Moroccan Darija and Modern Standard Arabic where appropriate:
 - Use Darija for informal or conversational parts.
 - Use Standard Arabic for formal or widely recognized scientific terms. Do your best to find most suitable translations.
 - If translating certain phrases would sound awkward, unclear, or artificial in Darija, then translate them in Standard Arabic.

GOAL:

Make the content clear and naturally understandable to Moroccan Arabic speakers while respecting the technical integrity of the original text. Return the translated text without saying anything else.

Examples:

Example 1 (Code + Explanation)

Input:

The 'Function' `calculate_mean(data)` is used to compute the average of a list of numbers.

```
// This function iterates through the list
// and calculates the sum. Python
```

```
def calculate_mean(data_list):
    # Calculate sum of elements
    total_sum = sum(data_list)
    # Calculate number of elements
    count = len(data_list)
    # Return the mean
    return total_sum / count
```

Its 'Complexity' is O(n).

Output:

ال 'Function' `calculate_mean(data)`
 كتستعمل باش نحسبو المعدل ديال شي
 ليستة ديال الأرقام.

// هاد الدالة كدور على العناصر
 Python وكتحسب المجموع.

```
def calculate_mean(data_list):
    # Calculate sum of elements
    total_sum = sum(data_list)
    # Calculate number of elements
    count = len(data_list)
    # Return the mean
    return total_sum / count
```

O(n) ديالها هي 'Complexity' ال.

Example 2 (Math Formula)

Input:

Consider the quadratic equation $ax^2 + bx + c = 0$. The solutions can be found using the formula:

$x = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$. This is known as the quadratic formula.

Output:

ناخدو المعادلة من الدرجة الثانية
 الحلول ديالها كتلقاوا $ax^2 + bx + c = 0$.
 بهاد الصيغة:

هادي معروفة بصيغة $x = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$.
 المعادلة من الدرجة الثانية.

Example 3 (Fully Regular Text)

Input:

This chapter introduces the basic concepts. Please read it carefully.

Output:

هاد الجزء كييعرف بالمفاهيم الأساسية.
عافاك قراه مزيان.

Now, translate the following text:

A.1.2 Comprehensive Description of Source Datasets

Comprehensive Description of LIMA-1k Dataset:

The LIMA-1k dataset, introduced in (Zhou et al., 2023), comprises 1,000 meticulously curated examples specifically designed to efficiently align large language models (LLMs) with minimal computational resources. This dataset originates from an initiative exploring the hypothesis that effective alignment and instruction-tuning do not necessarily require extensive datasets or reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF). Instead, the primary goal of LIMA-1k is to demonstrate that alignment can predominantly be achieved by leveraging the knowledge already embedded within pre-trained models, with fine-tuning merely instructing the model in stylistic and structural nuances for interacting effectively with users.

LIMA-1k is curated from several high-quality online sources, notably Stack Exchange, wikiHow, and selected Reddit communities (r/WritingPrompts), augmented with manually authored examples to enhance stylistic uniformity and thematic diversity. Table 3 summarizes the dataset’s key statistics.

Data Source	Examples	Avg. Input Length	Avg. Output Length
Stack Exchange (STEM)	200	117	523
Stack Exchange (Other)	200	119	530
wikiHow	200	12	1,811
Pushshift Reddit r/WritingPrompts	150	34	274
Natural Instructions	50	236	92
Manually Authored (Group A)	200	40	334
Total/Average	1,000	93	727

Table 3: Summary statistics of the LIMA-1k dataset (Zhou et al., 2023).

Below are representative multi-turn dialogue examples illustrating the conversational coherence and stylistic uniformity achieved by LIMA-1k.

Example 1:

Human: Tell me an interesting fact about geography.

Assistant: Here are some interesting facts about geography:

- **Bhutan** is one of the most intriguing places in the world. The Buddhist kingdom is the only carbon-negative country on Earth, with strict environmental laws and cultural norms that preserve its stunning natural landscape. For similar reasons, Bhutan was one of the last countries to introduce television in 1999, and has no traffic lights to this day.
- There are currently few territories on Earth that are unclaimed by any sovereign state (*terra nullius*). One example is **Bir Tawil**, along the border between Egypt and Sudan, which was created by a discrepancy between borders drawn in 1899 and 1902. The territory remains unclaimed by either country because it would entail forfeiting the much larger Halaib Triangle, which is claimed by both countries. Bir Tawil has no settled population, but the land is used by Bedouins who roam the area.
- The **antipode** of any spot on Earth is the point directly opposite to it on the globe. Interestingly, most land areas’ antipodes fall in the ocean. For instance, the antipode of Spain is in New Zealand, but the antipode of most locations in North America lies in the Pacific Ocean.

Example 2:

Human: I am planning to start a book club with some friends. Can you write an email invitation for the same?

Assistant: Here is an example email invitation for a book club:

Subject: Join me for a book club!

Hi [Friend’s Name], how are you?

I’m starting a book club with some friends, and I’d love to have you join us!

The book club is a casual and fun way to read and discuss books that we love or want to learn more about, and also make new friends. We plan to meet more-or-less once a month.

We're thinking of having our first meeting on **[Date & Time]**. Could that work for you?

Would love to see you there!

Thanks,
[Your Name]

The significance of LIMA-1k lies in its exceptional efficiency and effectiveness. Remarkably, despite its modest size of only 750,000 tokens, models fine-tuned on LIMA-1k exhibit robust generalization capabilities and compete closely with extensively trained RLHF models. This dataset convincingly demonstrates the practicality of minimal yet highly curated datasets for achieving high-quality alignment, substantially reducing computational costs and democratizing the capability for effective model alignment.

Comprehensive Description of DEITA-6k Dataset

DEITA-6k is a meticulously curated dataset of **6,000 instruction-response pairs** selected from a pool of **300,000 high-quality public instruction datasets**, including ShareGPT (58k), UltraChat (105k), and WizardLM (143k). It is designed to be the *smallest effective collection* that still achieves state-of-the-art alignment quality after SFT on 7B- and 13B-parameter models.

Selection Methodology The DEITA pipeline employs three criteria for selection:

- **Complexity (c):** Measured using an EVOL-COMPLEXITY scorer trained to evaluate the reasoning depth of instructions.
- **Quality (q):** Assessed using an EVOL-QUALITY scorer focusing on the helpfulness and informativeness of responses.
- **Diversity:** Ensured by applying a cosine similarity threshold ($\tau = 0.9$) over sentence embeddings to avoid redundancy.

The final score $s = c \times q$ ranks the samples, and the highest-ranked examples satisfying diversity constraints form the DEITA-6k dataset.

Key Statistics:

Statistic	Value
Total Examples	6,000
Source Pools	ShareGPT (58k), UltraChat (105k), WizardLM (143k)
Average Input Length Ceiling	2,048 tokens
Domain Coverage	Balanced across 8 MT-Bench categories
Complexity Gain vs Random	+0.43 MT-Bench (6.46 \rightarrow 6.03 on LLaMA-13B)
Quality Gain vs Random	+3.17% AlpacaEval (77.08% \rightarrow 73.91%)
Scaling Insight	3K DEITA items match the performance of 300K examples

Representative Examples:

Example 1: Entain's Competitors Discussion

Human: list me some of Entain's competitors in their industry

Assistant: Entain, formerly known as GVC Holdings, is a multinational sports betting and gaming company. Competitors include:

1. Flutter Entertainment
2. William Hill
3. Bet365

Human: competitors who are also expanding into esports, game development

Assistant: Companies include:

1. DraftKings
2. FanDuel
3. Betway
4. Unikrn

Human: what studios has Unikrn acquired? Furthermore, elaborate on acquired:

Assistant: As of my knowledge cutoff, Unikrn has not acquired any gaming studios. Explanation of acquisitions:

1. Tencent/Riot Games: Full acquisition over time.
2. Tencent/Supercell: Majority stake through a consortium.
3. Activision Blizzard: Complete acquisition of Vivendi Games.

Example 2: IP Ownership and Business Model

Human: I have ownership of the IP of video games created by S2 Games excluding Heroes of Newerth... What is the appeal of this, to any

investor?

Assistant: Key appeals include:

1. Nostalgia and a loyal player base.
2. Unique IP and lore for expansion.
3. Use of AI-generated art and modern features.
4. Platform potential for indie developers.
5. Revenue-sharing model incentives.
6. Strong growth potential with community engagement.

Example 3: Data Warehouse Simplifications

Human: explain data warehouse architecture in easy language

Assistant: A data warehouse collects data from various sources, transforms it, and stores it centrally. Main components:

1. Data Sources
2. ETL Process
3. Data Warehouse
4. OLAP System
5. Front-End Tools

Example 4: Contracted Chief Brand Officer's Role

Human: Generate a description of a Contracted Chief Brand Officer's role

Assistant: A Contracted Chief Brand Officer becomes an integral part of your executive team, leading brand strategy and development, working with internal teams and external creatives to build a competitive brand presence, and providing ongoing strategic advisement.

Summary:

DEITA-6k demonstrates that **quality, complexity, and diversity can be engineered simultaneously** to produce a highly effective dataset for alignment. Despite its compact size, it enables language models to achieve near-SOTA performance with significantly reduced computational costs.

Comprehensive Description of TULU-50k Dataset

Comprehensive Description of TULU-50K Dataset

Origin and Purpose:

TULU-50K is a 50 000-example SFT subset dis-

tilled from the public TULU 3 SFT pool (≈ 939 k dialogues) released by the Allen Institute for AI. The subset was produced with the **MIG** (Maximising Information Gain) sampler (Chen et al., 2025), which automatically balances *quality*—measured by DEITA scores—and *diversity* in a semantic label-graph. Its primary goal is to offer an open, compact yet high-coverage instruction-following corpus for research on post-training large language models, especially where full-scale SFT mixes are computationally prohibitive. The data are licensed ODC-BY and are entirely in English.

Selection Method:

MIG first tags every dialogue in the 939 k-sample pool with semantic topic labels, then scores each instance with DEITA quality metrics. It models the tag space as a weighted graph, propagates information across semantically-related tags, and greedily selects examples that yield the highest marginal information gain—provably achieving a $(1 - 1/e)$ approximation of the optimal subset. Compared with random or purely quality-based filtering, the resulting 50 k set delivers state-of-the-art downstream scores while cutting sampling time by two orders of magnitude.

Some Examples:

Example 1:

Human: Captain Jake, a somewhat short-tempered commercial airline pilot, has to navigate a complex flight path to avoid airspace controlled by airlines embroiled in corporate squabbles. The flight path consists of a series of vectors in 3-dimensional space. Each vector represents a leg of the journey from one waypoint to another.

- 1. Given the following vectors representing legs of the journey:
 - Vector A: $\mathbf{a} = (3, 2, -1)$
 - Vector B: $\mathbf{b} = (-2, 4, 5)$
 - Vector C: $\mathbf{c} = (1, -3, 2)$

Calculate the total displacement vector \mathbf{d} from the start to the end of the journey. Express \mathbf{d} in its simplest form.

- 2. Captain Jake needs to maintain a steady altitude change to avoid turbulence caused by corporate squabbles in certain airspace layers. If the journey described by vector \mathbf{d} must ensure that the vertical displacement

(z-component of \mathbf{d}) is zero, determine the required adjustment vector $\mathbf{e} = (x, y, z)$ such that the modified displacement vector $\mathbf{d}' = \mathbf{d} + \mathbf{e}$ satisfies this condition. Additionally, compute the magnitude of the adjustment vector \mathbf{e} .

Assistant: Let's break down the problem into the given tasks and solve each part step by step.

1. Calculate the total displacement vector \mathbf{d} :

Given vectors:

$$\mathbf{a} = (3, 2, -1), \quad \mathbf{b} = (-2, 4, 5), \\ \mathbf{c} = (1, -3, 2)$$

The total displacement vector is:

$$\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b} + \mathbf{c}$$

Compute each component:

$$\mathbf{d}_x = 3 + (-2) + 1 = 2, \\ \mathbf{d}_y = 2 + 4 + (-3) = 3, \\ \mathbf{d}_z = -1 + 5 + 2 = 6$$

So, the total displacement vector is:

$$\mathbf{d} = (2, 3, 6)$$

2. Determine the adjustment vector \mathbf{e} :

We want $\mathbf{d}' = \mathbf{d} + \mathbf{e}$ such that the z-component of \mathbf{d}' is zero:

$$6 + z = 0 \implies z = -6$$

Thus, $\mathbf{e} = (x, y, -6)$. Since only the vertical displacement needs correction, we can choose $x = 0$ and $y = 0$ for simplicity. Therefore:

$$\mathbf{e} = (0, 0, -6)$$

The magnitude of \mathbf{e} is:

$$|\mathbf{e}| = \sqrt{0^2 + 0^2 + (-6)^2} = \sqrt{36} = 6$$

Final Answer: The displacement vector is $\mathbf{d} = (2, 3, 6)$, and the magnitude of the adjustment vector \mathbf{e} is 6.

Example 2:

Human: A dedicated spectator named Alex spends their weekends analyzing basketball player statistics to provide data-driven recommendations. Alex

has been tracking the performance of a team throughout the season and has compiled a dataset consisting of the following metrics for each player: points per game (PPG), assists per game (APG), rebounds per game (RPG), and a newly devised metric called *Efficiency Rating* (ER), which is calculated as:

$$ER = (PPG \times 0.4 + APG \times 0.3 + RPG \times 0.3)$$

- **1.** Alex wants to determine the optimal combination of players in a 5-person lineup to maximize the team's average Efficiency Rating. Given that there are 10 players on the team, develop an algorithm or mathematical model that can identify the best combination. What is the maximum possible average Efficiency Rating for the team?
- **2.** After selecting the optimal lineup, Alex decides to project the team's overall performance in the upcoming playoffs. Alex uses a regression model where the team's winning probability in a game is given by:

$$P(\text{win}) = 0.5 + 0.1 \times (\text{average ER of the lineup})$$

Assuming the optimal lineup maximizes the team's average ER to 25, calculate the probability of the team winning a best-of-7 series, where the team must win 4 out of 7 games to advance.

Assistant: Let's solve the problem in two parts.

1. Optimal Lineup to Maximize Average ER:

- Sort the 10 players by their Efficiency Rating (ER).
- Select the top 5 players with the highest ER values:

$$ER_1 \geq ER_2 \geq ER_3 \geq ER_4 \geq ER_5$$

- Calculate the maximum average ER:

$$\frac{ER_1 + ER_2 + ER_3 + ER_4 + ER_5}{5}$$

- According to the problem, the maximum average ER is given as 25.

2. Projecting the Team's Winning Probability:

Using the regression model:

$$P(\text{win}) = 0.5 + 0.1 \times 25 = 0.5 + 2.5 = 3.0$$

Since probabilities cannot exceed 1, the model saturates at:

$$P(\text{win}) = 1$$

Probability of Winning a Best-of-7 Series:

- The team must win 4 out of 7 games. - If $p = 1$, the team is certain to win each game.
- Therefore, the probability of winning the series is effectively:

$$P(\text{series win}) = 1$$

Final Answer: The maximum possible average Efficiency Rating is 25, and the team has a theoretical 100% chance of winning the best-of-7 series under the given model.

Concluding Remarks:

TULU-50K strikes a pragmatic balance between dataset footprint and skill coverage. Empirically, models fine-tuned on this 50 k slice match or exceed full-pool baselines on both knowledge-centric (ARC, MMLU) and preference-centric (AlpacaEval v2, MT-Bench) benchmarks while slashing compute and curation time. Its transparent provenance, permissive license, and rich per-sample metadata make it an efficient, community-friendly test-bed for exploring data-centric alignment questions and rapid prototyping of instruction-tuned LLMs.

A.2 Illustrative Examples from Final Darija Datasets

A.2.1 Illustrative Examples from Darija Lima

See Figures 1 and 2.

A.2.2 Illustrative Examples from Darija Deita

See Figures 3, 4, and 5.

A.2.3 Illustrative Examples from Darija TULU

See Figures 6 and 7.

A.3 Efficiency and carbon footprint

Protocol. We follow the GREEN 500 methodology and the recommendations of Strubell et al. (2019); Henderson et al. (2020). The total electrical energy E for a training run is

$$E = \sum_{g \in \{\text{A100, H100}\}} N_g t_g P_g \text{PUE } \eta,$$

where N_g and t_g are the number of GPUs and wall-clock hours, P_g is the average power draw (350 W for A100-80 GB (Corporation, 2024), 500 W for H100-80 GB), PUE = 1.3 is a modern data-centre power-usage effectiveness, and $\eta = 0.9$ down-scales for the fact that accelerators seldom sustain their full TDP for an entire job.

Our training budget. Table 4 lists every experiment reported in Section 4. All ablations on the 4 B backbone consume a *combined* 10 GPU-h on A100-80 GB, while the GEMMAROC run uses 48 GPU-h on H100-80 GB. Plugging these figures into the formula above gives:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\text{A100}} &= 10 \text{ h} \times 0.35 \text{ kW} \times 1.3 \times 0.9 = 4.1 \text{ kWh}, \\ E_{\text{H100}} &= 48 \text{ h} \times 0.50 \text{ kW} \times 1.3 \times 0.9 = 28.1 \text{ kWh}, \\ E_{\text{total}} &\approx 32 \text{ kWh}. \end{aligned}$$

With a 2024 global mean grid-carbon intensity of 0.40 kg CO₂/kWh (Agency, 2024) this implies

$$C_{\text{ours}} \approx 13 \text{ kg CO}_2\text{e}.$$

Baselines: Atlas-Chat. Atlas-Chat 27 B used LoRA rank 256, 3 epochs over 500 k sequences of length 2 048 ($\simeq 675$ M training tokens)—and used the GEMMA-2-27B as its base model. A recent vLLM benchmark on a single A100-80 GB reports an *inference* throughput of $\approx 5 \times 10^2 \text{ tok s}^{-1}$ for Gemma-2-27B (Databasemart, 2025). Training carries out a forward *and* a backward pass; empirical FLOP analyses therefore divide inference speed by ~ 3 . We conservatively adopt $r = 55 \text{ tok s}^{-1} \text{ GPU}^{-1}$.

$$\begin{aligned} t_{\text{wall}} &= \frac{675 \times 10^6}{8 r 3600} \approx 4.26 \times 10^2 \text{ h}, \\ t_{\text{GPU}} &= 8 t_{\text{wall}} \approx 3.41 \times 10^3 \text{ GPU-h}. \end{aligned}$$

Using the NVIDIA A100-80 GB SXM4 average training draw $P = 0.35 \text{ kW}$ (NVIDIA, 2024) and an industry-average PUE of 1.3 with 90 % utilisation, the energy and carbon footprints are

$$\begin{aligned} E &= t_{\text{GPU}} P \text{PUE } 0.9 \approx 1.4 \text{ MWh}, \\ C &= E \times 0.436 \text{ kg CO}_2\text{e kWh}^{-1} \approx 610 \text{ kg CO}_2\text{e}. \end{aligned}$$

Run	GPUs	Hours	GPU·h	Purpose
Gemma-3-4B-LIMA	2×A100	0.4	0.8	1 K single-turn
Gemma-3-4B-DEITA	2×A100	0.8	1.6	6 K dialogue
Gemma-3-4B-DEITA ⁺	2×A100	0.8	1.6	+30
Gemma-3-4B-TULU	2×A100	3	6	50 K reasoning
<i>Subtotal 4 B</i>			10	
Gemma-3-27B-TULU	8×H100	6	48	final GEMMAROC
Total	—	—	58	

Table 4: Revised energy-accounting input reflecting the updated 10 A100 GPU-h for all 4 B experiments.

(Ember and Institute, 2024)

Finally, at a public on-demand rate of \$2 A100-h⁻¹ the run would cost \sim \$6.8k, underscoring the budget advantage of our own (far cheaper) fine-tune.

A.4 Training and Eval Loss of GemMaroc-27b

كيفاش تكون سعيد فزواج ماشي سعيد؟

الناس كيفا فزواج ماشي سعيد لأسباب بزاف. إذا كنت واحد من هاد الناس، تقدر تحس براسك ما يمكنش تكون فرحان. على الرغم من هادشي، تقدر تلقى طريقتك الخاصة للسعادة، حتى فشي وضعية خايبة، بممارسة عادات اللي كتوصل للسعادة، وحتى تقدر تخدم على الزواج ديالك باش توصل للسعادة كزوجين.

###تعلم تكون سعيد

1. قلب على طرق باش تكون ممتن. ماشي ديما ساهل تكون ممتن، خاصة وسط علاقة خايبة. على الرغم من هادشي، الامتنان يقدر يعاونك باش تواجه العلاقة الخايبة، ويقدر يوصلك باش تكون سعيد. خود الوقت كل نهار باش تعرف شنو ممتن ليه. حاول تكتب شي حاجات ممتن ليه كل نهار فواحد الجورنال. تقدر تستعمل حتى المنشورات اللي فال social media لهاد الغرض. غالبا، واخا تكون الوضعية خايبة، تقدر تلقى شي حاجة تكون ممتن ليه. مثلا، تقدر مابعجيكش كيفاش كيتعاملو معاك فالعلاقة اللي فيها، ولكن تقدر تكون ممتن لأن عندك استقرار مالي فحياتك ف هاد الوقت. أولا، تقدر تكون ممتن لأن الطرف الآخر فالعلاقة كيبقى أب أو أم مزبانه لولدك.

2. شارك ف 'flow experiences' لحظات ال Flow هي فاش كتتسى راسك فواحد التجربة بكونك مندمج كليا فشنو ما كنت كبير. إلا كنت فنان، كاتب، ولا حتى عداء، تقدر تكون ديما فهمتي هاد النوع ديال التجارب. هاديك اللحظة اللي كيطيح فيها العالم، و أنت غير كتجرب و لا كتستمتع باللي كبير. الدراسات بينات باللي كلما كانو عندك لحظات Flow بزاف، كلما كنت سعيد بصفة عامة. اختار شي نشاط اللي كيتحدالك شوية، ولكن اللي يكون مألوف باش تقدر تنسى راسك فيه. مثلا، إلا كنت كتستمتع برسم المناظر الطبيعية، تقدر تجرب ترسم موضوع جديد بحال شي بورتريه ولا شي طيسيل ديال الفواكه.

3. حبس من نفس المشاكل. يعني، إلا كنت ديما كتلقى راسك كتجادل على نفس الحوايج، يمكن وصل الوقت باش تحط هاد الموضوع على جنب. خاصك تقرر باللي ماغاديش تناقش فيه حيث مايمكنش تتفقو و لا تحاولو تلقاوا شي حل وسط اللي يخدم ليكم بجوج. مثلا، إلا كنتو كتجادلو بزاف على السياسة، تقدر تبغيو تخليو السياسة موضوع ممنوع. و لا، إلا كنتو كتجادلو بزاف على شنو من فيلم غادي تشوفو فالليلة ديال الجمعة، تقدر تبغيو تناوبو فالإختيار ديال الفيلم.

4. طور الإهتمامات الخاصة ديالك. إلا الزواج ديالك ماشي هو اللي بغيته، يقدر وصل الوقت باش تلقى شي إشباع خارج الزواج ديالك و ماشي على شكل خيانة. أن تكون عندك هوايات و اهتمامات خاصة غادي يعاونك باش تبقى مستقل و تبقى سعيد و مندمج مع العالم. فالحقيقة، تطوير الإهتمامات الخاصة فكرة مزبانه حتى إلا كان عندك زواج زوين. فكر أنك تستكشف اهتماماتك فالمكتبة، و لا تنضم لأندية الهوايات المحلية أو دروس الطبخ، و لا تاخذ دروس مهنية فشي كلية مجتمعية قريبة [...].

###خدم باش يكون عندك زواج أحسن

1. خصصو وقت باش تكونو مجموعين. تخصيص الوقت لبعضكم البعض طريقة باش تقولو أنكم ملتزمين ببعضكم البعض. قولو بأنكم غادي تقضيو وقت معين كل أسبوع مع بعضكم البعض، و بقاوا عليه. غادي يعطيك حتى فرصة باش تعرفو بعضكم البعض من جديد.

2. تفكرو شنو كنتو كتقدروا. فاش يلاه تلاقيتو، غالبا كنتو منجذبين جزئيا للإختلافات اللي كان كيعرضها الطرف الآخر. مثلا، تقدر تكون كتفكر حقيقة أنه كان ولا كانت مندفعين و كيعجبهم يكونو عفويين. دابا، تقدر تلقى راسك كتكره هاد الصفة. المهم هو تحاول تتفكر علاش كنتي كتحب هاد الصفة فالأول و تولي تستمتع بيها من جديد. مثلا، تقدر تطلع ليك فالراس فاش الزوج ديالك يبغي يخلي كلشي و يسافر للجبال. من جهة أخرى، كتخلي حياتك ما توليش مملة بزاف. حاولو تلقاوا توازن، و استمتعوا باللي قدرتوا عليه [...].

Figure 1: Illustrative example 1 from Darija Lima dataset.

شرح مبسط ل encryption backdoors

كابينين جوج ديال المفاهيم لي شوية مستقلين على بعضياتهم ف backdooring ديال encryption algorithms:

*ال backdoor يقدر يكون explicit ولا implicit. ال explicit backdoor هو واحد لي كلشي عارف باللي راه كابين. أما ال implicit backdoor فيحاول يبقى مخفي على مالين ال algorithm بطبيعة الحال، فاش كيكون شي explicit backdoor ، الناس كيميلو يتجنبو ال algorithm بصفة عامة، يعني explicit backdoors ممكن يكون عندهم أمل باش يخدمو غير فوجود شي إطار قانوني لي يفرض على implementers يستعملو ال system لي فيه ال backdoor. مثال على شي explicit backdoor هو ال Clipper chip (لي تخلى عليه ف الأخير). ال backdoor مائشي بالضرورة يكون ف ال algorithm ، كثر ف التجميع ديال algorithms ف شي protocol ، و تقنيا كان عبارة على automatic key escrowing method. أما بالنسبة ل شي implicit backdoor ، شوف ال Dual EC DRBG كمثال مشهور: كان كيخدم غير إلى مكان تا واحد عارف باللي فيه backdoor.

*ال security ديال ال backdoor يقدر يكون quantifiable ، ولا لا. ف حالة ديال Dual EC DRBG ، ال mechanism كيستعمل طرق رياضية معروفة: ال NSA كانت عارفة باللي استغلال ال backdoor كيطلب معرفة ديال شي internal secret (key، مبني على discrete logarithm على elliptic curves).

شي security مائشي quantifiable هو لي كيوقع فاش كتحاول تدفع شي algorithm لي فيه عيب متعدد، ولا شي واحد لي عارف عليه شي cryptanalytic method لي ما نشر تيهش. هادي لعبة خطيرة بزاف بالنسبة ل شي وكالة تجسس، حيث مايمكنش تعرف واش أطراف آخرين يقدرؤا يلقاؤ العيب ولا لا. بحال هاد ال backdooring كيقلب عليك ف المدى الطويل.

لي مثير للاهتمام، ال NSA ما كتميلش تستعمل non-quantifiable backdoors. مثال مزيان هو DES. ف الوقت لي تصمم فيه، ال NSA كانت معتقدة باللي تقدر تواجه شي upfront 256 exhaustive search ، و باللي حتى واحد آخر (خصوصا السوفييات) ما عندوش ال technology و ال budget باش يدير هادشي. ال NSA كانت عارفة حتى على شي cryptanalytic method جديدة (differential cryptanalysis) يعني فاش ال NSA تدخلت ف التصميم ديال DES ، أصرت باش تنقص ال key من 64 ل 56 bits هادي إضافة ديال شي quantifiable backdoor ، و كانت واضحة بزاف، يعني شبه explicit ، و أيضا باش تقوي التصميم ضد differential cryptanalysis. هادا مثال مزيان على كيفاش ال NSA تجنبات بو عي شي non-quantifiable backdoor. كابين حاجة وحدة لي وكالات التجسس كيخافو منها كثر من أنهم ما يقدرؤو يتجسسو: هي الفكرة باللي وكالات تجسس منافسة أخرى ممكن حتى هي تتجسس.

إذن شي backdoor حقيقي و مزيان هو لي كيستعمل maths باش يعطي شي quantifiable security ضد الاستعمال الغير مصرح به ديال ال backdoor. صعب بزاف يكون عندك quantifiable security بلا ما تجعل ال backdoor explicit. "الأفضل ف فنتها" ف هاد المجال هي Dual EC DRBG ، و حتى قبل ال Snowden business ، ال cryptographers كانوا كيشوفوها غريبة بزاف و شكاؤ بقوة ف شي تلاعب) شوف ال analyses ف 2007 ، 6 سنين قبل Snowden.

Figure 2: Illustrative example 2 from Darija Lima dataset.

Human:

خطوة بخطوة بمنظور عام certificate pinning process أهلا، بغيتك تشرح ليا ال

Assistant

أكيد! ها هي خطوة بخطوة شرح لعملية certificate pinning بمستوى عالي:

1. ال client (API أو website بحال) server كيبدأ اتصال ب (mobile app أو web browser بحال) client ال.
 2. ومعلومات تعريفية أخرى public key ديالو، اللي كيتضمن SSL/TLS certificate كيجابوب ب server ال.
 3. trusted بحال ليستة ديال trusted root authorities مع مجموعة ديال certificate كيدير فحص لل client ال (Certificate Authorities عند ال client مخزنة عند ال).
 4. server وكيدير اتصال آمن مع ال SSL/TLS handshake كيكمل عملية client موثوق، ال certificate إلا كان ال.
 5. معرفة مسبقاً، واللي متخزنة pins مع مجموعة ديال server ديال ال certificate كيغيريفي client خلال هاد العملية، ال localement عند ال client.
 6. يقدر وياكونوا pins هاد ال:
 - a) Public key pins: hash ال public key ديال ال server ديال ال (SHA-256 بحال)
 - b) Certificate pins: hash ال certificate ديال ال (SHA-256 كامل بحال)
 7. اللي معرفين مسبقاً، الإتصال كيدار. و إلا ماكانش، ال pins من ال pin كيطابق مع شي server ديال ال certificate إلا كان client ال SSL/TLS handshake كيرفض الإتصال وكيسالي ال client.
 8. يقدر يعطي للمستخدم رسالة تحذيرية أو يأخذ إجراءات أخرى باش ينبه pin validation واجه فشل في client إلا ال. المستخدم للخطر الأمني المحتمل.
- بإختصار، certificate pinning هي آلية كتسمح لل clients يتأكدو باللي كيتواصلو مع ال server المقصود ماشي محتال. عن طريق مقارنة SSL/TLS certificate ديال شي server مع مجموعة ديال pins معرفة مسبقاً، ال clients يقدر وياخففو من الخطر ديال (MITM) attacks وأنواع أخرى ديال certificate-based attacks.

Figure 3: Round 1 of an Illustrative example from Darija Deita dataset.

Human:

واش هادشي كييعني باللي أي API call كنستعملو فيه axios مثلاً غادي يكون secure ؟

Assistant

شهادة التثبيت بوحدها ما كتضمنش بأن كل API call كتستعمل مكتبة بحال Axios غادي تكون آمنة، حيث كاينين ثغرات محتملة أخرى في التطبيق و الشبكة اللي ممكن تستغل. ولكن، certificate pinning تنقص بشكل كبير من خطر هجمات الوسيط (MITM) (man-in-the-middle attacks)، اللي هي واحد من طرق الهجوم الشائعة في بزاف ديال الاختراقات الأمنية.

ملي كطيلقي certificate pinning مع Axios ولا أي مكتبة HTTP client أخرى، مهم تبع أحسن الممارسات وتأكد بأن ال client مكونفيگوري باش يغيريفي ويثبت الشهادة ديال السيرفر بشكل صحيح. بالزيادة على هادشي، تدابير أمنية أخرى خاصها تطبق، بحال output encoding و input validation، باش تنقص بشكل أكبر من خطر الثغرات الأمنية.

باختصار، فاش certificate pinning إجراء أمني مهم، خاصها تستعمل بالاقتران مع ممارسات أمنية أخرى باش نتأكدو بأن API calls اللي كتستعمل Axios ولا أي مكتبة أخرى تكون آمنة قدر الإمكان.

Figure 4: Round 2 of an Illustrative example from Darija Deita dataset.

Human اوکي، کیفاش نقادو axios باش نستعملو certificate pinning ؟

Assistant

باش تصاوب Node.js ف `https` module ، ممکن تستعمل ال certificate pinning باش تخدم Axios باش تکنيفيگوري معرفين مسبقا. ها هو pins واحد المجموعة ديال against ديال السيرفر certificate لي کیفاليدي ال HTTPS agent واحد ال :واحد المثال کیفاش دبر هادشي

```
1  ```javascript
2  const https = require('https');
3  const axios = require('axios');
4
5  // Define the list of pins as an array of SHA-256 hashes
6  const pins = ['sha256/xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx',
7  'sha256/yyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyyy'];
8
9  // Create a custom HTTPS agent with pin validation
10 const agent = new https.Agent({
11   pinning: true,
12   checkServerIdentity: function(host, cert) {
13     const certPins = cert.getPublicKey().getFingerprints();
14     for (let pin of pins) {
15       if (certPins.has(pin)) {
16         return undefined; // Certificate is valid
17       }
18     }
19     return new Error('Certificate pin validation failed');
20   }
21 });
22
23 // Use the custom HTTPS agent with Axios
24 const instance = axios.create({
25   httpsAgent: agent
26 });
27
28 // Make a secure API call with Axios
29 instance.get('https://example.com/api/data')
30   .then(response => {
31     console.log(response.data);
32   })
33   .catch(error => {
34     console.error(error);
35   });
```

فهاد المثال، أول حاجة كنديفينيو واحد ال array ديال SHA-256 hashes لي كيتمثل اللانحة ديال ال pins لي بعينا نقاليديو ال certificate ديال السيرفر against ها. من بعد كنصاوبو واحد ال HTTPS agent باستعمال ال `https.Agent` constructor ، وكنحطو ال `pinning` option ل `true` باش نفعل ال pin validation.

من بعد، كنديفينيو واحد ال `checkServerIdentity` function لي كتعيط ليها فاش كيوصل ال certificate ديال السيرفر. هاد الدالة كتجد ال SHA-256 fingerprints ديال ال public key ديال ال certificate وكتفارنهم مع اللانحة لي معرفة مسبقا ديال ال pins. إلا تلاقى شي match ، الدالة كترجع `undefined` ، وكاتبين باللي ال certificate صحيح. إلا مالقاتش شي match ، الدالة كترجع واحد ال `Error` object بواحد ال message لي كيبين باللي ال pin validation فشل.

أخيرا، كنصاوبو واحد ال instance ديال Axios باستعمال ال `axios.create()` method ، وكنحطو ال `httpsAgent` option ال HTTPS agent ديالنا. ديك الساعة ممكن نصاوبو واحد ال secure API call باستعمال ال `instance.get()` method ، لي غيستعمل ال agent ديالنا باش يقاليدي ال certificate ديال السيرفر against ال pins ديالنا لي معرفين مسبقا.

لاحظ باللي هادا غير واحد المثال کیفاش تکنيفيگوري Axios باش تخدم certificate pinning ، وكابنين طرق أخرى باش تنفذ هاد ال feature على حساب ال specific use case وال environment ديالك.

Figure 5: Round 3 of an Illustrative example from Darija Deita dataset.

Human سير ل URL التي جاي باش تبتدا التحليل الشامل ديال التطور العالمي ديال التطعيم ضد COVID-19
[https://raw.githubusercontent.com/owid/covid-19-](https://raw.githubusercontent.com/owid/covid-19-data/master/public/data/vaccinations/vaccinations.csv)
(data visualization) التي كتمثل مجموعة البيانات المعقدة بشكل مفهوم.

Assistant

باش تصاوب شي تصويرة فعالة و عندو معنى، خاص تكون عندك فهمة واضحة للمعطيات والقصة التي كتعاود. ها بعض الطرق COVID-19 ديال التلقيح ضد dataset المبتكرة لتصور المعطيات التي تقدر تفكر فيها بالنسبة لهاد

1. ****Time-Series Analysis****:
هادي تقدر تكون الخطوة الأولى فين كتحلل التقدم ديال التلقيح مع مرور الوقت. هادشي ممكن تمثلو ب Line Plots ، فين محور السينات (x-axis) كيمثل الوقت، ومحور العيانات (y-axis) كيمثل عدد التلقيحات. خطوط مختلفة تقدر تمثل بلدان مختلفة.
2. ****Geo-mapping****:
ممكن تستعمل Geographical Heatmaps باش تبين التغطية ديال التلقيحات ضد COVID-19 فالعالم. المناطق التي فيها الظلال غامقة كتمثل أعداد كبيرة ديال التلقيحات. هادشي غايغطي نظرة واضحة كيفاش المناطق المختلفة كتمشي فالنقدم ديال التلقيحات.
3. ****Comparison Dashboard****:
دحل bar charts ولا pie charts التي كتقارن نسب التلقيح بين بلدان مختلفة، وكيبينو الدول التي قريبة من مناعة القطيع (herd immunity).
stacked bar ولا line charts ممكن تستعمل باش تبين النسبة ديال الجرعة الأولى إلى الجرعة الثانية ديال التلقيحات لكل بلد.
4. ****Trend Analysis****:
بين المعدل باش كل دولة كتلقح السكان ديالها. لهادشي، استعمل خط بياني فين محور السينات (x-axis) كيشير للوقت ومحور العيانات (y-axis) كيبين التلقيحات اليومية. خطوط مختلفة تقدر تدل على بلدان مختلفة.
5. ****Correlation Heatmap****:
هادا غادي يساعد في فهم كيفاش شي parameter (بحال مجموع التلقيحات ولا الناس التي تلقحو) مرتبط ب parameters أخرى (بحال مجموع السكان ولا النسبة المئوية ديال السكان).
6. ****Aging Analysis****:
عرض الأعمار ديال الناس التي كياخدو اللقاح بدمج معطيات التلقيح مع معطيات ديموغرافية.
7. ****Vaccine Type Analysis****:
في حالة إلى ال dataset كيتضمن النوع ديال اللقاح التي تعطى، ممكن تصاوب dashboard كيمثل اللقاحات الأكثر استخداما فالعالم، ولا شي robust chart كيبين استخدام اللقاحات في بلدان مختلفة.
تذكر، التصورات خاص ديما تكون تفاعلية باش تعاون المستخدم. أدوات بحال Tableau, Power BI, Python libraries بحال Matplotlib, Seaborn, Plotly, ولا JavaScript libraries بحال D3.js ممكن تستعمل باش تصاوب هاد التصورات القوية.

Figure 6: Illustrative example 1 from Darija TULU dataset.

Human كتب دالة لي ماشي عي تبدل كاع ليسباس فالسلسلة النصية ب '39##&20%;39##&'; ولكن حتى تحيد أي ليسباس كايين فالأول و الآخر قبل ما تبدل. إضافة على هادشي، الدالة خاصها تخدم مع ليسباسات المتتابعين، يعني تبدلهم ب '39##&20%;39##&'; وحدة. الدالة خاصها تكون حساسة لحالة الأحرف (case-sensitive)، يعني تفرق بين الحروف الكبيرة و الصغيرة.

باش نزيدو الصعوبة، الدالة خاصها تبدل أي تواجد للحروف 'a'، 'b'، 'c' بالقيم ASCII ديالهم بصيغة hexadecimal. التبدل خاصو يكون case-sensitive، يعني 'A'، 'B'، 'C' خاصهم يتبدلو بقيم مختلفة على 'a'، 'b'، 'c'. الدالة خاصها تخدم مع التكرارات المتتالية ديال هاد الحروف و تبدلهم بقيمة hexadecimal وحدة مناسبة.

علاوة على ذلك، الدالة خاصها تقدر تخدم مع سلاسل نصية الطول ديالها كيوصل ل 1 مليون حرف. الدالة خاصها تكون مهينة للسرعة و ما تستعملش شي دوال مدمجة للتلاعب بالسلاسل النصية.

Assistant تنفيذ بحال هاد ال 'functionality' بكفاءة، خصوصا بلا ما نعتمدو على ال built-in string manipulation 'functions'، كيتجاوز القدرات ديال شي لغة interpreted بحال Python و JavaScript لي كتستعمل عادة في 'interactive mode'.

ولكن، ها واحد الطريقة ب Python مع شوية ديال ال built-in functions باش نفهمو مزيان:

```

1- def replace_chars(string):
2   string = string.strip()
3   nspaces = 0
4   result = ''
5   ascii_hex = {'a': '%61', 'b': '%62', 'c': '%63',
6               'A': '%41', 'B': '%42', 'C': '%43'}
7
8-   for char in string:
9-       if char.isspace():
10          nspaces += 1
11-         if nspaces == 1:
12             result += '%20'
13-         else:
14             nspaces = 0
15-             if char.lower() in ascii_hex:
16-                 if not result.endswith(ascii_hex[char]):
17                     result += ascii_hex[char]
18-             else:
19                 result += char
20
21   return result

```

هادشي ماجاوبش على السؤال ديالك نيشان حيث كيتستعمل ال built-in string manipulation functions، بسبب التعقيد اللي عايكون ضروري باش نتفاداو كاع هاد الدوال.

لغة بمستوى أدنى بحال C++ أو Rust عادي تكون مناسبة كثر لهاد المستوى ديال ال string manipulation و optimization. بشكل عام، بحال هاد ال constraint بحال عدم استخدام ال built-in functions والتعامل مع سلاسل نصية فيها حتى لمليون حرف مع تبديلات معينة (ماشى بالضرورة يكون مطلوب في تطوير التطبيقات، و كيشبه لشي مهمة متخصصة و بمستوى منخفض ديال التعامل مع النصوص).

أيضا، مهمة التعامل مع سلسلة نصية فيها حتى لمليون حرف كتطلب تفكير عميق في إدارة الذاكرة (memory management)، شي حاجة لي اللغات ذات المستوى الأدنى كتكون مؤهلة ليها أحسن. إضافة على ذلك، تقنيات ال optimization بحال string pooling، استخدام هيكل بيانات محددة (eg. ropes or gap buffers) كيتدارو بشكل أحسن بلغات ذات مستوى منخفض. إذن، هادا موضوع متقدم كيتطلب معرفة بلغة صديقة لل compiler، فهم ال ASCII character sets، و ال memory management. نمنصح باستشارة مهندس برمجيات (software engineer) أو مطور متخصص في تحسين الأداء و ال string manipulation.

Figure 7: Illustrative example 2 from Darija TULU dataset.

Figure 8: Training loss (per step) for GemMaroc-27B over 1 300 global steps, showing a rapid decline from 3.5 down to 1.3 as the model learns.

Figure 9: Evaluation loss at each validation checkpoint (every 50 steps), reaching its minimum (0.915) at global step 900 (\approx 2 epochs), indicating that after just two passes over the data we obtain our most powerful fine-tuned model.